

D.O.M.E LENS SUPPORT MOUNTING GUIDE

DESIGN YOUR OWN MULTIMEDIA LEARNING ENVIRONMENT (D.O.M.E.)

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1. Preparation

It is necessary to print the parts in a 3D printer start this part of the project.

1.1 To be printed

We based this plans to 3D print, instructions and other materials in the Planets in a Room project (www.planetsinaroom.net), which are distributed under Creative Commons Attribution - Non commerciale - Non opere derivate 4.0 Internazionale.

Important: All dimensions here are in mm; the recommended Material is PLA and ABS*; the recommended print resolution** is less than 0.2mm.

Part to be printed:

- 1 piece of 03_Wheel_A_1x;
- 1 piece of 02_Wheel_B_1x;
- 8 pieces of 01_Wheel_C_8x;
- 1 piece of 04_Sphere_Support_Plane_1x;
- 1 piece of 05_Projector_Support_Base_1x;
- 1 piece of 06_Projector support_plane_1x;
- 1 piece of 07_Mirror_Support_1x;

To be easier the name of the file has the quantity to be printed at the end.

Figure 1 - Objects to be 3D printed, note they are not in scale.

*for the best result please select for the “06_Projector support_plane_1x” material and filling with good thermal characteristics, for the other parts you can use PLA or other materials

**the best resolution is needed for the “07_Mirror_Support_1x” part the other part are less critical

1.2 Materials needed

Here is a list of the materials we need, and the minimum quantity for one complete optical system in the D.O.M.E. project. Some of these objects are already specified in the Mounting Guide for the cardboard planetarium, however we will copy these specification.

Tips: If you need, it is possible to adapt some details in this list: change all the different Hexagonal Nuts to 6 mm kind; change all the threaded rod to 6 mm kind.

Figure 2 - Materials needed to the optical system of D.O.M.E. Project.

Material	Specification	Quantity
Wing Nut	(D) M6 nuts easy to turn	4 units
Threaded rod	(E) 6 mm thick (M6) and 200 mm length	4 units
Hexagonal Bolt	(F) M8 x 80 mm fully threaded	1 unit
Hexagonal Bolt	(G) M8 x 40 mm fully threaded	2 units
Hexagonal Nut	(H) M8 self-locking nut	2 units
Hexagonal Nut	(I) M8 nuts	3 units
Hexagonal Nuts	(J) M6 nuts for the threaded rod	20 units
Flat Mirror	40 x 40 mm, inner the structure of the optical system	1 unit
50 mm lens	(lens 1) lens with f1.8 and adapted for CANON and large aperture cameras	1 unit
Fisheye Lens	(lens 2) f3.5 and 8 mm focal length	1 unit

LED projector	4,000 Lumens Full HD 1080p LED projector	1 unit
Computer	A commercial computer to use the software	1 unit

2. Mounting

2.1 The lens support

The mounting scheme is pretty easy and direct, as we can see below.

2.2 The projector support

2.3 All together

Now we need to put the lens and the projector in each own support and link the computer to the projector.

Lens1

Lens 1 must be wedged and
Focus on infinite.

The lens 1 fits correctly in the support, let the focus on infinite for this lens. The projector support should be inclined until the projector lens is aligned to the lens 1.

Lens2

The lens 2 is free move on the plane, this movement is important to adjust the resolution of the projected image. The focus of this lens should be set to infinite and the diaphragm opened to maximum.

3. Adjusts

Finally, we have the projector system mounted and now we need to project the images and videos inside the dome. Like explained in the D.O.M.E. Mounting Guide, the lens support should be in the centre of the planetarium, it means, the fisheye lens should be aligned with the centre of the first pentagon mounted.

Now, we turn on the system (computer + projector) and the images are a little bit blurred (the stars aren't points). We need to adjust the lens array.

Of course, we can reset the height of the optical support (a) or the inclination of the projector (b). Remember, the point here is always keep the lens 1 and the projector lens aligned. However, you always can up both if you need the horizon higher (considering the Stellarium projection).

Usually, setting the relative distance between the lens support and the projector (moving 'c' and/or 'd') reach a good resolution of the projected image.

Important: If the system is moved for any reason, we should proceed this adjustment again.